

2. Lahiri, "Indian River and River Systems-The Genesis of Article 262 of the Constitution of India and the Interstate River Water Disputes Act, 1956- Developments till 1949"
3. Philippus Wester and Jeroen Wamer, "River basin management reconsidered," in *Hydropolitics in the Developing World: A Southern African Perspective*, eds. Anthony Turton and Roland Henwood eds, (African Water Issues Research Unit, 2002)
4. Mark Tully and Satish Jacob, *Amritsar: Mrs Gandhi's Last Battle*, Rupa Publication, 1985
5. Ramaswamy Iyer, "Punjab water imbroglio: Background, implications and the way out," *Economic and Political Weekly*, July 31, 2004, 3435-8.
6. Neil Smith, 1992. *Geography, difference and the politics of scale*. In *Postmodernism and the social sciences.*, eds. Joe Doherty, Elspeth Graham and Mohammed H. Malek, 57-79. New York: St. Martin's Press.

⌘⌘⌘

Effect of Meditation on the Mental Health of Undergraduate Students

Jitendra Kumar Pal

Research Scholar, Dept. of Education,
K.M.C. Language University, Lucknow

Prof. Chandana Dey

Head, Dept. of Education,
K.M.C. Language University, Lucknow

Abstract

This research is aimed to examine the effect of meditation on the mental health of undergraduate students. The sample consisted of 30 undergraduate students from Vidant Hindu P.G. College, University of Lucknow, with the age group of 18–22 years by purposive sampling. The intervention was given every morning 15 minutes before class hours for 30 teaching days. The data were collected through the Mental Health Battery developed by A.K. Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta. The data were statistically analysed, and a statistically significant difference was observed between the pre- and post-intervention impact of meditation on the mental health of undergraduate students, given the $t = 6.46$, $DF = 29$, threshold value (Table value) = 2.045, 95% CI. The study's outcomes indicate that meditation positively affects undergraduate students' mental health.

Key Words: Yoga, Meditation, Mental Health, well-being.

Introduction

According to Svetasvatara Upanisad (6.21) human entire life has divided into four Ashramas or stages (Macdonell & Keith, 1912, p.1, 68 as cited in Brockington, 1995). Brahmacharya (student's life), Grihastha

(householder), Vanaprastha (hermit) and Sanyasa (renouncer). The first phase carries special significance for physical and mental health. One in six people is aged 10-19 years (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Being the formative period with major impacts on the future, it's become one of the most crucial period of life. It is a very sensitive and challenging part of life. In this stage, along with physical, mental and emotional changes, children and adolescents also undergo moral, social and psychological changes. One in 10 girls under the age of 20 has been a victim of sexual violence. Fifteen million girls under the age of 18 get married every year (UNICEF, n.d, as cited in Zenele, 2016). In such a situation, males and females both have to fight with many problems and challenges and accordingly, they have to develop proper combinations at all levels. Worsley and Williams (2020) survey report warns that the COVID-19 pandemic could have a 'deep' and 'pervasive influence' on global mental health now and in the future, and advocates for mental health and brain science research to be at the forefront of the worldwide response to the epidemic. Patel, et al. (2018) stated that "no health without mental health."

The world has been changing in a rapid way, especially the revolutionary developments in Information Communication Technology and Artificial Intelligence. International Telecommunication Union (ITU) estimates that approximately 5.3 billion people or 66 per cent of the world's population are using the internet in 2022. In the present day, youngsters spend a substantial time of the day on the internet and due to this some of the commonly observed dysfunctions have been found to include a decline in academic performance, discontinuation of studies, financial losses, interpersonal conflicts and poor mental health. The Presence of co-occurring mental and substance use disorders is another significant findings among these cases (Balhara et al. 2017). In every part of the world,

poor mental health causes suffering for children and young people. It is a top cause of death, disease and disability, especially for older adolescents (UNICEF, n.d.). The study conducted by Kessler et al. (2007) and Patel et al. (2007) indicates the first onset of mental disorders usually occurs in childhood or adolescence, although treatment typically does not occur until several years later. Roughly half of all lifetime mental disorders in most studies start by the midteens and threefourths by the mid20s. Although interventions with early incipient disorders might help reduce the severity persistence of primary disorders and prevent secondary disorders research is urgently required to enhance affordable and feasible interventions. The researcher tried to investigate affordable and preventive measures through meditation to improve the mental health of onset. The objectives of this research was to examine the effects of meditation on the mental health of Undergraduate Students.

Mental Health

The World Health Organization (WHO) define "Mental health is a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to make a contribution to his or her community". Mental health is not merely the absence of infirmity but more relative in its concept to the daily life actions we carry out to maintain psychological resilience. Mental health is the ability to adjust satisfactorily to the various strains of the environment that we meet in life. Good mental health makes a vibrant contribution to the overall health and well-being of individuals and our communities. Good mental health is very important at every stage of life because it can affect physical health. However, when mental health is compromised, it is not always clearly visible and understood by people. There are certain warning symptoms to look out for, that may indicate negative changes in the mental health

of the individual. Healthy eating habits, daily exercise and good sleep help to maintain good mental health and well-being. In various countries, awareness about mental health and rare availability of clinical facilities, especially in middle and low-income countries (WHO, n.d.) The Government of India has launched the National Mental Health Programme (NMHP) in 1982 to ensure the availability and accessibility of minimum mental healthcare.

Meditation

Meditation is an ancient Indian art as well as science which helps to improve physical, mental, and spiritual health. In the world, meditation has a variety of practices of focusing one's mind on a specific point or thing for a while. The meditative state brings the entire human expression into restraint. People believe that meditation is an approach to enriching "spiritual life". The implementation of meditation as a practise has demonstrated positive effects on students' overall health.

In Patanjali Yoga Sutra Maharishi Patanjali has described Ashtanga Yoga in the second chapter of Sadhan Pada. As stated in 'ya maniyama sanapranayama pratyaharadharanadhyanasamadhayo-ashtavaangani' (Y.S. 2/29), the first two are Yama and Niyama. Yama and Niyama similarly consist of five observances. They are social and ethical in nature. The next three Asana, Pranayama and Pratyahara are ways to restrain the individual. Last three are Dharna, Dhyana and Samadhi. Meditation is the seventh limb of Ashtanga Yoga. The act of concentration or contemplation on a subject is called meditation. Maharishi Patanjali says, "tatra pratyaya-ekatânatâ dhyânam" (Y.S. 3/2½- Concentration on the object perceived is meditation. That means the mind is at the place of perception. In Sankhya philosophy Maharshi Kapil says, "dhyanam nirvishayam manah" (Sa.da.6/25). Meditation is the becoming free of the objects of the mind. The Human mind remains fickle

due to having desires for objects. Therefore, meditation is to stop the mind from the subjects and engage in self-contemplation. Meditation entails the uninterrupted stream of cogitation directed towards a singular entity or deity.

In ancient Indian scriptures, various modes of meditation have been described. There are three types of meditation mentioned in Gheranda Samhita, "sthûlam jyotisthâ sukmaA dhyânasya trividham vidu%" (Gh.Sa.6/1). Engaging in meditation is commonly recognised as the sixth limb of yoga, posited by the esteemed Maharshi Gherand. The dhyana is of three types Sthula, Jyotirmaya and Sukshma. Meditation involves four basic tenets: (1) focusing of thought upon a constant stimulus, e.g. repetition of a sound, a word, or fixed gazing upon a specific object (2) passive attitude and disregard for distractible stimuli (3) decreased muscle tone and (4) quiet environment (Benson, et al., 1974).

Review of Literature

The Indian way of life suggests numerous simple practices which can be incorporated into our daily life to make them more wholesome. And meditation is one of them. Everyone, child, adult and old can practice yoga and meditation. It is simple and vital and doesn't require any special equipment and place. Meditation has been practiced for thousands of years. As Tripanchag Yog says (as cited in Akhand Jyoti, March, 1941, p.23).

"yatra yatra manoyati brahmanasthata darshanat manso dharanshchaiva dharansaparamta".

To achieve control over the mind, it is recommended to maintain a focus on Shri Bhagwan in any subject matter that the mind may wander towards. This approach involves cultivating a harmonious understanding of self-realization and consistently contemplating the presence of God in all things, including within one's own mind. These methods are considered to be straightforward and effective means of

achieving mental discipline.

An article in TIME magazine (2003) states that “Scientists study it. Doctors recommend it. Millions of Americans—many of whom don’t even own crystals—practice it every day. Why? Because meditation works.” Previous studies have also shown that meditation reduces poor mental health and relieves a variety of symptoms or distress (Loizzo, 2009). Meditation creates a state of harmony between the mind, body, and spirit, therefore, it is a foundation for holistic health (Yang et al., 2009). Years of scientific and clinical research have suggested that meditation is one of the safest and easy practices in complementary and alternative medicine; it is very effective to balance physical, emotional, and psychological states (Ramaswami & Sheikh, 1989). Other forms of yogic practices have been advocated for combat anxiety and stress and control one’s mental state, constipation, insomnia, headache, arthritis, asthma, and ‘rejuvenation’ (Pal & Dey, 2022; Banerjee, 2014; Gururaja, et al. 2011; Shapiro et al. 2007; Muktibodhananda, 1993).

Objective of the study

To investigate the effects of meditation on the mental health of undergraduate students.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant effect of meditation on mental health of undergraduate students.

Research Method

The present study is an experimental investigation conducted within a group (pre-post) design to evaluate the impact of meditation on the mental health of undergraduate students. The research was conducted on 30 undergraduate students enrolled at Vidyant Hindu P.G. College located in Lucknow. The study’s participants were selected through purposive sampling, encompassing both male and female individuals. The participants underwent pre- and post-meditation evaluations. Individuals who experienced significant mental or physical ailments were

prohibited from registering as students.

Instrument

Mental health Battery by Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta was used for data collection before and after the intervention. This battery consists of six indices of mental health: 1) Emotional Stability, 2) Overall adjustment, 3) Autonomy, 4) Security-insecurity, 5) Self-concept, 6) Intelligence. It is equally valid for males and females and there is no fixed time limit for the first five parts. Part VI is a speed test and the total allotted time for this is 10 minutes.

Intervention Procedure

The Meditation session was given to designated subjects for 30 instructional days during regular class hours. The study incorporated meditation sessions that were scheduled in the morning, specifically from 8:30 am to 9:00 am, with a prescribed minimum duration of 15 minutes. The participants were directed to adhere to the guidelines provided in the meditation. Meditation began with the adoption of the Sukhasana sitting posture, the utilisation of specific hand gestures, and the attainment of a state of equilibrium between the mind and body. Participants were instructed to maintain a stationary posture while shutting their eyes and engaging in silent contemplation and introspection of all emotions and perceptions related to their respiration. The effects of meditation on mental health were measured by administering the Mental Health Battery (MHB) before and after 30 days of practise.

Result

Obtained data were analyzed statistically using a paired sample t-test to assess the significance level within the group.

	Mean	N	SD	DF	t-value	Significance level
Pre-test	86.33	30	7.85	29	6.46	0.05
Post-test	100.66	30	12.56			

Table.1: Comparison of Mental health test scores before and after the Intervention

The Mean and SDs of pre and post-test of all subjects followed by t-value are shown in

the result table. When pre and post-test scores were compared to assess any difference, the post-test scores increased from 86.33 ± 7.85 to 100.66 ± 12.56 [average \pm standard deviation]. Changes were statistically significant given the $t = 6.46$, $DF = 29$, threshold value (Table value) = 2.045, 95% CI. The research findings suggest that the implementation of meditation has a beneficial impact on student's mental health. Figure no 1 shows the graphical representation of the data that was discussed above.

Discussion on Findings

The objective of the current investigation was to examine the impact of meditation on the mental health of undergraduate students. The study's results demonstrated significant evidence of meditation's effect on undergraduate student's mental well-being. Findings from the prior study have advocated a significant impact of meditation in reducing anxiety, stress and enhancing mental health and well-being (Priti et al. 2022; Engler, 2018; Carmody & Baer, 2008; Levine, 1989; Carrington et al., 1980). In recent decades, several studies have suggested the use of meditation in psychotherapy (Weiss et al. 2005; Allen et al. 2006; Kuijpers et al. 2007).

The act of meditation entails the process of developing and refining the cognitive faculties of the mind (Manocha, 2000). According to Brown and Ryan (2003), the practise of meditation enables an individual to attain a mental state characterised by heightened awareness of both internal and external events occurring in the present moment. According to Yang et al.

(2009) findings, practising meditation for a brief period of time can yield significant advantages. Meditation can assist students in coping with life's stresses. Meditation creates a meaningful state by coordinating the mind with the body. Maharshi Patanjali has considered the instincts of the mind (Chittavrittiya) to be the root cause of human problems. Meditation integrates it from all sides and plans them in one direction. Thus, Meditation is a unique practice, it has many positive consequences.

Conclusion

Meditation is a science that helps in the physical, mental, intellectual and spiritual development of humans. This study is grounded in an ancient traditional Indian meditation approach to enhance the mental health of college students, and its results are effectively supported. After Intervention post data score signifies that meditation is quite effective to enhance mental health. The study may benefit academicians, students, parents and social workers to improve mental health and reduce the severity/persistence of primary disorders.

References

- Aacharya, Shree Ram Sharma. (2000). Sankhya evam Yog Darshan. Gaytri Trust, Ved Vibhag, Shantikunj, Haridwar.
- All World Gayatri Pariwar (AWGP). (March, 1941). Atma Vishwash Ka Abhav. Akhand Jyoti, P.21 <https://literature.awgp.org/akhandjyoti/1941/March/v1.23>
- Allen, N. B., Blashki, G., & Gullone, E. (2006). Melbourne Academic Mindfulness Interest Group (2006). Mindfulness-based psychotherapies: A review of conceptual foundations, empirical evidence and practical considerations. Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry, 40(4), 285-294.
- Balhara, Y. P., Bhargava, R., & Chadda, R. K. (2017). Service development for behavioural addictions: AIIMS experience. Annals of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (India), 53(03), 131-139. <https://doi.org/>

10.1055/s-0040-1712755

Banerjee, S. (2014). Effect of Yoga on the Memory of Middle School Level Students. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 4(1), 49-52.

Benson, H., B., J. F., & Carol, M. P. (1974). The relaxation response. *Psychiatry*, 37 (1), 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.1974.11023785>

Brockington, J. (1995). *Patrick Olivelle: The Âúrama System: The history and hermeneutics of a religious institution*. xiii, 274 pp. New York and Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1993. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies*, 58(3), 580-581. doi:10.1017/S0041977X00013306

Brown, K. W., & Ryan, R. M. (2003). The benefits of being present: mindfulness and its role in psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 84(4), 822.

Carmody, J., Baer, R.A. (2008). Relationships between mindfulness practice and levels of mindfulness, medical and psychological symptoms and well-being in a mindfulness-based stress reduction program. *J. Behav Med* 31, 23–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-007-9130-7>

Carrington, P., Collings Jr, G. H., Benson, H., Robinson, H., Wood, L. W., Lehrer, P. M. & Cole, J. W. (1980). The use of meditation–relaxation techniques for the management of stress in a working population. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 22(4), 221-231.

Chadda R. K. (2018). Youth & mental health: Challenges ahead. *The Indian journal of medical research*, 148(4), 359–361. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijmr.IJMR_1585_18

Engler, J. (1984). Therapeutic Aims in Psychotherapy and Meditation: Developmental Stages in the Representation of Self. *The Journal of Transpersonal Psychology*, 16(1), 25-61.

Gururaja D., Harano K., Toyotake I, & Kobayashi H. (2011). Effect of yoga on mental health: Comparative study between young and

senior subjects in Japan. *International Journal of Yoga*, 4:7-12.

International Telecommunication Union. (n.d.). Statistics. <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Pages/stat/default.aspx>

Kessler, R. C., Amminger, G. P., Aguilar-Gaxiola, S., Alonso, J., Lee, S., & Ustün, T. B. (2007). Age of onset of mental disorders: a review of recent literature. *Current opinion in psychiatry*, 20(4), 359–364. <https://doi.org/10.1097/YCO.0b013e32816ebc8c>

Kuijpers, H. J., Van der Heijden, F. M. M. A., Tuinier, S., & Verhoeven, W. M. A. (2007). Meditation-induced psychosis. *Psychopathology*, 40(6), 461-464.

Levine, S. (1989). *A gradual awakening*. Anchor Books. <https://ixtheo.de/Record/1649086768>

Loizzo, J. (2009). Optimizing learning and quality of life throughout the lifespan: A global framework for research and application. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1172, 186-198.

Manocha, R. (2000). Why meditation?. *Australian Family Physician*, 29(12), 1135-1138.

Muktibodhananda, S. (1993). *Hatha yoga Pradipika*. Bihar School of Yoga.

National Health Mission (1982). <https://nhm.gov.in/index&level=2&sublinkid=1043&lid>

Pal, J.P. & Dey, C. (2022). *Bhartiyo Gantro Me Mansik Swasthya evam Manha Chikitsa*. *Bauddhik Bharat*, 9(1), 113-117.

Patanjali Yogsutra (2018). Gitapress, Gorakhpur

Patel, V., Flisher, A. J., Hetrick, S., & Mc Gorry, P. (2007). Mental health of young people: A global public-health challenge. *The Lancet*, 369(9569), 1302-1313. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(07\)60368-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(07)60368-7)

Patel, V., Saxena, S., Lund, C., Thornicroft, G., Baingana, F., Bolton, P., Chisholm, D., Collins, P. Y., Cooper, J. L., Eaton, J., Herrman, H., Herzallah, M. M., Huang, Y., Jordans, M. J. D., Kleinman, A., Medina-Mora, M. E., Morgan, E.,

Niaz, U., Omigbodun, O., ... Unützer, JÜ. (2018). The Lancet Commission on global mental health and sustainable development,. The Lancet, 392(10157), 1553-1598.

Shapiro, D., Cook, I. A., Davydov, D. M., Ottaviani, C., Leuchter, A. F., & Abrams, M. (2007). Yoga as a complementary treatment of depression: Effects of traits and moods on treatment outcome. Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine, 4(4), 493-502. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ecam/nel114>

Sharma, P., Malhotra, R. K., Ojha, M. K., & Gupta, S. (2022). Impact of meditation on mental & physical health and thereby on academic performance of students: a study of higher educational institutions of Uttarakhand. J. Med. P'ceutical Allied Sci, (11-12), 2309, 4641 - 4644. doi: 10.55522/jmpas.V11I2.2309

TIME Magazine. (2003). The science of meditation. TIME.com. <https://content.time.com/time/subscriber/article/0,33009,1005349,00.html>

United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund. (n.d.). On My Mind: Better mental health for every child. <https://www.unicef.org/on-my-mind>

Weiss, M., Nordlie, J. W., & Siegel, E. P. (2005). Mindfulness-based stress reduction as an adjunct to outpatient psychotherapy. Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics, 74(2), 108-112.

World Health Organization (WHO). (n.d.). Policy, law & rights. WHO. <https://www.who.int/teams/mental-health-and-substance-use/policy-law-rights>

World Health Organization. (2021, November 17). Adolescent mental health. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health>

World Health Organization. (n.d.). Mental health. World Health Organization (WHO). <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mental-health>

Worsley, R. & Williams, R. (2020). COVID-19 and Mental Wellbeing. <https://www.ipsos.com>

www.ipsos.com. <https://www.ipsos.com/en-uk/Covid-19-and-mental-wellbeing>

Yang, K. P., Su, W. M., & Huang, C. K. (2009). The effect of meditation on physical and mental health in junior college students: a quasi-experimental study. The journal of nursing research : JNR, 17(4), 261-269. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JNR.0b013e3181c17f77>

Yang, K., Su, W., & Huang, C. (2009). The effect of meditation on physical and mental health in junior college students. Journal of Nursing Research, 17(4), 261-269. <https://doi.org/10.1097/jnr.0b013e3181c17f77>

Zanele, M., Temitayo, E., & Kadidiatou, T. (2016). Young people's contribution to the Global strategy for women's, children's and adolescents' health (2016-2030). Bulletin of the World Health Organization, 94 (5), 312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2471/BLT.16.174714>

⌘⌘⌘